

DEVELOPMENT OF LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract: *This article provides information about the history and stages of development of landscape architecture.*

Key words: *Landscape, architecture, buildings, construction materials, aesthetic results, design.*

Landscape architecture is the design of outdoor spaces, landmarks, and structures to achieve environmental, socio-behavioral, or aesthetic outcomes.[2] It includes the systematic design and general engineering of various structures for construction and human use, the study of existing social, ecological and soil conditions and processes in the landscape, and the design of other activities that produce the desired results. The profession is broad and can be divided into several subcategories, including professional or licensed landscape architects, who are regulated by government agencies and have experience designing a wide range of structures and landforms for human use; landscape design that is not a licensed profession; site planning; stormwater management; fight against erosion; environmental restoration; parks, recreation and urban development; management of visual resources; green infrastructure planning and provision; and master planning and design of private property and residential landscapes; at various scales of design, planning and management. A practitioner of landscape architecture can be called a landscape architect, but in jurisdictions where professional licenses are required, often only those who hold a landscape architect's license can be called a landscape architect.«

The term "landscape architecture" appeared for the first time more than a hundred years ago in connection with the establishment of the first national parks in the United States. This concept came to Europe much later. But this does not mean that the history of landscape architecture is short. To imagine the years of development of landscape architecture, it is necessary to understand what landscape architects do and what place their profession occupies in the wider scale of architecture. being liq. horticulture developed in antiquity, and in the Middle

Ages it reached the level of park art. At the borders of the XIX and XX centuries, the activity of architectural planning and aesthetic organization of large urban and non-urban areas with the means of beautification and greening began to be called landscape architecture. Compared to the natural environment, this activity is an environment created by human hands. However, it is worth noting. the environment that architects create can vary in quality. First of all, it is an environment of artificially created areas, which are more or less separated from the environment. This environment consists of a wide variety of buildings and structures, including underground, mobile, etc. may consist of structures. All these spaces enclosed by walls and fences within buildings and structures belong to architecture. Another type of environment formed by architectural means is open spaces that are not enclosed by blocking structures. These include parks, gardens and squares, streets, avenues (boulevards), public spaces. These include waterfronts, quarter (guzar) interior spaces, historic landscapes, etc. The range of open spaces is huge and the list of their types can be continued endlessly. Landscape architecture deals with the formation of the environment of open spaces, that is, landscape architecture is the architecture of open spaces. The bright, originality of landscape architecture and its most important branch of garden-park art is the use of special, natural building materials: plants, water, land, and topography of the place are considered to have been used and are still being used. It is these materials that are the main working tools of landscape architecture in creating the environment of open spaces. Although conventional building materials are also important, they are only complementary to the environment being formed. [1] Therefore, landscape architects mainly work with the natural environment. In some cases, it interferes with the natural environment as little as possible, in other cases, it creates "artificial nature", that is, it forms a completely new environment of open spaces that arise as a result of architectural creativity. These two traditions, in their various combinations, are manifested throughout the entire history of the development of landscape architecture. The distinctive feature of landscape architecture when compared with the generally accepted architectural practice is the leading importance of the aesthetic and ecological-humanitarian basis. Functional and technical aspects of the created environment take a subordinate place, despite their importance. This quality became the basis for the understanding of landscape architecture as a type of art, precisely as garden and park art. At the same time, the field of landscape architecture is considered only by garden and park art, especially compared to previous periods, even by experts. restriction would be wrong. Until recently, this work was considered an

addition to architectural creativity based on the need to improve the environment of buildings and structures. For a long time, this activity was called landscaping. Usually, this work was and still is done by landscapers without the necessary professional training, or at best. However, major architects and urban builders were also engaged in the creation of urban open spaces in different periods. For example, the foundations of landscape architecture can include: agoras, forums and pedestrian streets of antiquity, as well as squares with sculptures and fountains from the Renaissance, Baroque and Classicism periods. Among the great works of landscape architecture of the past, we can include the Capitoline Square in Rome, with its steps, cobbled streets, the Peterbuig beaches and bridges with the sculptures created by the great Michelangelo, the works of the great local historian Felton and the works of a number of other architects. The next hundred years The field of activity of network architecture has expanded considerably. Now it includes even wider areas. For example, the entire area of the city, compared to a separate area, is combined with the concept of urban construction landscape. However, the organization of its landscape on the scale of covering the urban space goes beyond the scope of landscape architecture, this activity can now be called landscape urban construction. It should also be noted that a larger sum of urban, rural, technical and recreational landscapes is included in the concept of urbanized landscapes. In this case, urbanized landscapes are included in the general landscape of the earth's surface. However, as a result of the growth of urbanized landscapes, natural landscapes are partially destroyed. In this case, if new landscapes (urban or other) with a sufficient balance of green areas are not created in place of landscapes taken from nature, then the ecological balance of urban and suburban areas or ecological relations are broken, and the bigger the city, the more it affects the ecology of the environment. That is why the more global and complex landscape architecture includes urban and agricultural and other areas. is the regulation of the landscape environment of large areas.[3]

Conclusion:

Here, landscape architecture is combined with the third important field of architectural creativity - landscape planning within the framework of city planning at the level of district planning. A distinctive feature of landscape planning is the organization of spatial environments of large areas, in which the vertical measurement is very small compared to the scale of the plan. At this level, it is effective for the landscape architect to know the basics of economic geography, district planning, ecology and a number of other important branches of knowledge. As a result of modern globalization, the reduction of natural landscapes and the

inevitable increase of anthropogenic landscapes, landscape architecture has gone beyond the limits of the usual activities of architects. In the middle of the 20th century, landscape architecture became an independent direction. Modern landscape architecture is not only concerned with the formation of gardens and parks, but also deals with all types of open spaces, including urban, rural and inter-rural spaces. remains responsible for regulating relations. "Second nature" - the creation of architectural landscapes grows proportionally to the growth of society's needs. In the modern understanding, it can be said that landscape architects truly understand the relationship between man and nature. Despite the fact that the development of landscape architecture in different countries is not the same, its future is clear - the more people use nature, the more the field of activity for landscape architecture expands.

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